

OPTIMAL FEATURE EXTRACTION TECHNIQUES TO IMPROVE CLASSIFICATION PERFORMANCE, WITH APPLICATION TO SONAR SIGNALS

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Abstract

Feature extraction is an important preliminary step to classification of complex signals. By reducing a high-dimensional signal to a lower-dimensional feature set which preserves the relevant structure of the signal, classification performance is enhanced. A classification system was developed to classify sonar signals as to whether the object detected is minelike or non-minelike. Results are presented comparing classification performance when various feature extraction methods are implemented.

INTRODUCTION

Our objective is to extract pertinent features from acoustic signals in order to develop an automated classifier for sonar signals. The specific application in this case is classification of underwater mines, but this technique could be readily applied to other types of sonar signals. We have used sonar images of the sea bottom which contain sonar returns generated by mines of various types. The purpose of the classifier is to confirm the presence of a mine, and then to ultimately determine what type of mine is present. The emphasis in here is not the classifier itself, but the process of feature extraction which produces a projection of the signal in a lower dimensional feature space, thus improving classifier performance.

The results that will be presented in this paper show successful implementation of feature extraction algorithms in a system for sonar signal classification. Results are described for a two-class (mine and rocks) and four-class (three mine types and rocks), with a comparison of results using several methods of preprocessing.

FEATURE EXTRACTION

In many of the classification systems currently used, the process of feature extraction is relatively ignored in comparison to the method of classification itself. This is due to the fact that in many classification techniques, neural networks in particular, the process of feature extraction is inherently embedded in the classification technique rather than being apparent as a separate process. If a multi-layer neural network is used to classify unprocessed data, the input layer, which learns from examples, will essentially become a feature extractor. Also, the increased availability of computational power enables complex data to be classified with less preprocessing.

However, in problems such as machine vision, speech identification or the problem posed here of detecting objects in sonar returns, the input dimensionality of the problem becomes an impediment to classification. Even neural networks are limited by the problem of parameter estimation- as the number of parameters increases, the size of the data required to train the network increases faster. For a complex problem, obtaining the necessary data may be expensive or even impossible.

Much has been written about this dilemma, known commonly as the *curse of dimensionality*[1]. Because of the inherent sparsity of high-dimensional spaces, an inordinate amount of training data is required to obtain reasonably low variance estimators. The objective of feature extraction is to reduce the dimensionality of the data before performing classification. This is based on the assumption that the important structure in the data actually lies in a much lower dimensional space. If the transformation from the high dimensional space to the low dimensional space is accomplished without losing much relevant information, classification performance will be enhanced.

Thus the optimal method of classification of high dimensional data is a two step process: feature extraction which projects the original data to a lower dimensional feature space; and then performing classification in the low dimensional space. An important consideration is that the features obtained must be independent of class membership, because at this point in the process the class to which the data belongs is not yet known.

DESIGN OF THE FEATURE EXTRACTION/CLASSIFICATION SYSTEM

An overall scheme for preprocessing a given acoustic signal (each sonar return consisting of either a minelike object or a non-minelike object such as a rock), reducing it to a set of features, and using the feature set as an input to an

automated classifier was developed and implemented. Various types of learning algorithms and signal processing techniques were used to perform the preprocessing. These methods include Bienenstock, Cooper and Munro (BCM) learning theory, principal components analysis, and several types of transforms (Karhunen-Loeve, FFT, and wavelets). Results for some of these techniques are described here; other results will be available shortly and will be included in the final paper.

THE BCM ALGORITHM

Modification of synaptic effectiveness between cortical neurons is widely believed to be the physiological basis of learning and memory, and there is evidence that similar synaptic plasticity in many areas of mammalian cortex. In 1982, Bienenstock, Cooper and Munro[2] proposed a concrete synaptic modification hypothesis in which two regions of modification (Hebbian and anti-Hebbian) were stabilized by the addition of a sliding modification threshold. The BCM theory was originally created to explain the development of orientation selectivity and binocular response in various visual environments in kitten striate cortex, one of the most thoroughly studied areas in neuroscience.

In the BCM model, a change in the weight of a synapse is equal to the product of the presynaptic activity and a certain function (ϕ) of the postsynaptic activity. The qualitative consequences of the theory follow from a few properties of the ϕ function:

- when the postsynaptic activity is above the modification threshold (Θ_m), ϕ is positive (i.e. an active synapse will be potentiated);
- when postsynaptic activity is below Θ_m , ϕ is negative (i.e. an active synapse will be depressed);
- there is no activity ($\phi = 0$) when postsynaptic activity is equal either to the spontaneous firing rate or to Θ_m ;
- the value of Θ_m is not fixed, but rather "slides" as a function of the postsynaptic activity.

It is the selectivity of BCM neurons that makes this approach so suitable to the problem of feature extraction. In a BCM network, a small number (say, six) of BCM neurons are connected, with lateral inhibition introduced into the connections. In the architecture used here, the k th BCM neuron is inhibited by the 1st through $(k-1)$ th neurons. Thus, a small network of BCM neurons is capable of providing a set of distinct features from an input signal. The usual approach is to train the neurons on a combined set of samples of each type of data (i.e., in an n -

class classification problem, train on all n classes together). The class separability characteristic inherent in BCM neurons yields a set of features which tends to be very effective in identification of the distinct classes.

Previous research presented by the author [3] has demonstrated the capability of the BCM learning rule to perform feature extraction from acoustic signals. In this study, both single BCM neurons and networks of laterally-inhibited BCM neurons were trained on samples of marine mammal sounds. The result of this process is a weight vector (or set of vectors in the multiple neuron case) which, when convolved with a signal of interest, constitutes "testing". The output of the convolution process can then be input into an automated classifier (feed-forward neural network, nearest neighbor, etc.). The results obtained by testing on two types of marine mammals (porpoise and dolphin) demonstrated the capability of BCM neurons to become distinctly selective to one type of signal

MODEL DESCRIPTION

The design of the BCM-based classifier is depicted in Figure 1 (the overall schematic for classifier systems employing other preprocessing techniques is essentially the same). A network of laterally-inhibited BCM neurons is constructed; the number varies depending on the problem, but in the work described here 6 neurons were used. A parameter that adjusts the degree of inhibition between neurons is set; the optimal degree of inhibition is generally determined by performing several training runs and observing how well the value of Θ_m converges as this parameter is adjusted.

Examples of data from each class are used to train the BCM network. As discussed previously, this is an unsupervised procedure- the classes of the data must be assumed unknown at this point. Training the neurons on only one type of data will result in features that are dependent on the class of data used for training- thus they will not be effective to achieve separability between classes. Thus, if we are attempting to ascertain if a sonar return is of a mine or a rock, we must train the BCM network on a combined set of mine and rock data.

The result of this process is that a set of BCM weight vectors is produced. The number of vectors will be the same as the number of BCM neurons in the network; the length of the vector is of a predetermined length, as appropriate for the type of signal. When using acoustic data, the procedure is to sample each set

Figure 1. Schematic of BCM-based classifier system

of data randomly by running a window over it (typically of length 512 or 1024) and obtaining a vector of that length.

Next, the dot product of the signal to be tested and the set of BCM weight vectors is computed. The resultant vectors comprise the feature set to be used for classification. In all of the experiments described in this paper, a feed-forward neural network, using a standard backpropagation algorithm, was used. The intention here is not to focus on the classifier itself, but the process of constructing the inputs to the classifier. In order to train the classifier, the testing of the BCM network is first done with data of known classification; then the procedure is done with the trained classifier to determine the classification of an unknown sample.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The above described procedure was performed with various sets of real data (obtained from surface ship sonars) and sets of synthetic data. In order to provide a benchmark for classifier performance, many of the tests were repeated using wavelet or FFT preprocessors as well as BCM feature extraction; all with classifiers of comparable architecture. The results in the comparison studies using these three techniques were that BCM consistently performed as good as or better than wavelet preprocessing; both methods were consistently better than FFT preprocessing.

Figure 2 shows the results of testing on a set of data obtained by using sets of sonar returns from minelike and non-minelike objects that were denoised as much

as possible; then noise was incrementally introduced to the signals to produce a set of sonar returns of varying SNR. The classification results using BCM, wavelet, and FFT preprocessing were plotted versus the SNR for the various signals. In this example, BCM produced the best results in the mid-range of the curve. While the actual SNR values here might not be the same as a "real" mine classification problem, it is the middle of the curve that is most significant. When the SNR is close to zero, no classifier is going to do much better than a random guess. When the SNR is high, any classifier will have a good chance of performing well, but real sensors are generally not able to achieve this level of SNR, particularly in the shallow water environments of interest to the Navy.

The technique can also be applied to problems with more than two classes. In one experiment, samples of returns were used containing three types of mines (two bottom mines and one close-moored mine) as well as

Figure 2. Comparison of Percent Correct Classification of Mines vs. SNR for BCM, wavelet and FFT preprocessing

	B1	B2	CM1	ROCK
B1	0.873	0.087	0.016	0.024
B2	0.085	0.882	0.018	0.015
CM1	0.012	0.036	0.942	0.010
ROCK	0.040	0.032	0.017	0.911
	B1	B2	CM1	ROCK
B1	0.592	0.087	0.154	0.167
B2	0.160	0.622	0.142	0.076
CM1	0.144	0.085	0.688	0.083
ROCK	0.104	0.206	0.016	0.674

Table 1. Comparison of four class problem with BCM (top) and FFT (bottom) preprocessing

rocks. The SNR of the signals is not considered in this problem. The confusion matrix of the classification results, comparing BCM with FFT preprocessing, is shown in Table 1. The percent of correct classification when BCM was employed ranged from 87% to 94% among the classes; when FFTs were used the results ranged from 59% to 69% correct.

CONCLUSIONS AND ONGOING RESEARCH

We have developed and demonstrated an automated classifier for acoustic signals using the BCM learning procedure to perform feature extraction. The results obtained in the various classification problems support the contention that the BCM algorithm is an effective means of obtaining features for the purposes of classification. We will continue to run similar classification problems using the various feature extraction methods to determine the optimal method, which might depend on the type of signal to be classified.

Ongoing work is emphasizing the multiple class problem, and comparing the approach of using a one or two levels of classification. The multiple mine type classifier may be posed as a two level classification problem, as a sonar return from a submerged object is first classified as minelike or non-minelike, and then minelike objects are identified as a particular type of mine.

A particular area of interest at present is determining the characteristics of the features that the BCM neurons identify in minelike objects. For example, a trained sonar operator determines that an object is minelike by observing several characteristics (size, shape, reverberation, shadow, aspect) in the sonar image. We are presently attempting to ascertain if the features derived by BCM are analogous.

Another method that promises to achieve good classification performance is using genetic algorithms to obtain the best feature set for the classifier. Our work with this approach is too preliminary to present results at the moment, and will be presented in a follow-on paper.

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